

RIGOUROUS -
secuRe desIGn and deplOyment of trUsthwoRthy
cOntinUum computing 6G Services

Deliverable 6.3

DISSEMINATION REPORT

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Explanation/ Definition
EBOS	EBOS TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT-FI	ICTFICIAL OY
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ITAV	INSTITUTO DE TELECOMUNICACOES
LNVO	LENOVO DEUTSCHLAND GMBH
ONE	ONE SOURCE CONSULTORIA INFORMATICA LDA
ORO	ORANGE ROMANIA SA
OULU	OULUN YLIOPISTO
PU	Public
Starion	Starion LUXEMBOURG SA
UMU	UNIVERSIDAD DE MURCIA
UWS	UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND
WINGS	WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IKE
WP	Work package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Dissemination Report (D6.3) provides an overview of the communication and dissemination activities carried out during the RIGOUROUS project (i.e., M1 to M36). Building on the dissemination and communication plan outlined in Deliverable D6.2, the consortium implemented a coordinated strategy to maximize visibility, engage stakeholders, and ensure the long-term impact of the project's scientific, technological, and societal outcomes.

The dissemination activities were organized around four key pillars: academic dissemination, industrial and standardization engagement, community-building and open-source collaboration, and wide-reach communication actions. The project successfully met or exceeded nearly all Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), demonstrating the effectiveness of the approach and the commitment of all partners.

Academic dissemination was notably successful, resulting in a substantial number of high-quality scientific publications in top-tier journals, conferences, and workshops. Throughout the project's three phases, the consortium produced significantly more publications than initially targeted, reflecting the relevance and maturity of RIGOUROUS's findings across areas such as federated learning, cybersecurity, anomaly detection, secure onboarding, decentralized trust, and zero-trust architectures. Partners engaged in major international events, organized seminars and workshops, and supported advanced training at the MSc and PhD levels, integrating RIGOUROUS research into academic curricula.

The project also made a significant impact in industrial and standardization contexts through active participation in organizations like 3GPP, ETSI, ITU-T, and 6G-IA. Contributions from partners, especially Lenovo and UMU, helped shape ongoing discussions on zero-trust security, security monitoring, decentralized identity, trusted application onboarding, AI-enabled security mechanisms, and 6G security architecture proposals. RIGOUROUS surpassed its KPI of making at least four contributions, submitting numerous formal papers across multiple releases and study items.

Community-building efforts were strengthened through collaborations with other Horizon Europe and SNS projects, contributions to open-source initiatives, and involvement in SNS JU clustering activities. The development of open-source repositories and integrations with ETSI OpenSlice ensured transparency, accessibility, and future reusability of RIGOUROUS technologies.

Wide-reaching dissemination activities also had a significant impact. The RIGOUROUS website attracted nearly 5,000 visitors by Phase 3, far exceeding the target of 500. Social media engagement, promotional materials, newsletters, and video demonstrations amplified communication efforts, reaching both specialized and general audiences. Participation in public-facing events, such as the European Researchers' Night, helped connect advanced research with society.

In summary, the activities described in this report illustrate a successful dissemination strategy. The consortium's engagement and contributions to scientific, industrial, and standardization ecosystems ensured high visibility, credibility, and lasting impact for the project's outcomes. The foundations established by RIGOUROUS will continue to support future exploitation, standardization adoption, and research beyond the project's conclusion.

1 INTRODUCTION

Building on the dissemination and communication plan outlined in Deliverable D6.2, this Dissemination Report (D6.3) provides an overview of the communication and dissemination activities carried out during the RIGOUROUS project (i.e., M1 to M36). The consortium implemented and executed a coordinated strategy to maximize visibility, engage stakeholders, and ensure the long-term impact of the project's scientific, technological, and societal outcomes.

The document is organized into eight main sections, each focusing on a key aspect of the project's dissemination strategy and outcomes. **Section 2: Dissemination Strategy** articulates the overall dissemination philosophy, detailing specific objectives, key performance indicators (KPIs), and targeted stakeholder groups. This section establishes the foundational approach that guides all subsequent activities. **Section 3: Academic Dissemination** lists and describes outreach initiatives, including peer-reviewed publications, conference presentations, the organization of local workshops and international seminars, and advanced training opportunities. **Section 4: Standardization Activities** outlines the project's engagement with standard-developing organizations (SDOs), highlighting both active participation and significant contributions to the development or formulation of relevant standards. **Section 5: Communities of Interest** describes activities that promote knowledge sharing and collaboration within broader communities. It covers open-source repository management, synergies with other Horizon Europe/SNS projects, and engagement in wider innovation networks, including the SNS JU. **Section 6: Communication Activities** discusses high-visibility outreach mechanisms, such as maintaining the project website, developing promotional materials, managing social media and newsletters, and disseminating information through technology demonstrator videos. **Section 7: Conclusions** synthesizes the overall impact of the dissemination strategy, reflecting on key outcomes, lessons learned, and strategies for maintaining project visibility after completion.

2 DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

In Deliverable 6.2 (D6.2), we have outlined the RIGOUROUS Dissemination and Communication plan, which will serve as the basis for this report.

2.1. Objectives and KPI

The following activities were planned and executed:

- **Public website:** WP6 created a comprehensive public website containing all relevant information about the project. It provided centralized access to various publicly available deliverables, publications, and articles related to the project. The site was regularly updated throughout the project's lifetime with publications and publicity materials, including flyers, posters, public deliverables, organized workshops, available services, and more.
- **Social networking:** The project developed its presence on social networks and media. These channels were used to interact with both the professional community (researchers, SMEs, and large industry) and the general public, while carefully addressing privacy and data protection concerns. The participation of Consortium members in public events, key achievements, publications, and software releases was announced through established social networking platforms such as LinkedIn and YouTube.
- **Promotional material:** The project prepared appropriate printed materials to promote the project's outcomes to the general public and developed a graphic identity to support the other dissemination activities of RIGOUROUS. In addition, the consortium produced press releases to publicize the project's progress and created other promotional materials highlighting RIGOUROUS's main goals and achievements (e.g., flyers, fact sheets, roll-ups, videos, electronic posters, quarterly newsletters, and other printed material).
- **Participation in third-party events (research/academic, industry, others):** The RIGOUROUS consortium worked to ensure the project's presence in third-party events relevant to its scope, including participation in scientific conferences, workshops, seminars, innovation events, tradeshows, exhibitions, organization of special sessions at reference conferences and workshops, demonstrations, and other activities that led to the engagement of a broad spectrum of audiences from different backgrounds. This approach helped increase the project's visibility and impact, as well as the visibility of its research topics.
- **Organization of local workshops:** RIGOUROUS organized local workshops colocated with the project's plenary meetings, held in different countries. The goal was to conduct one-day workshops for relevant stakeholders. Each workshop provided an overview of RIGOUROUS and highlighted innovations, including short presentations from invited stakeholders and related research projects. This approach proved to be a cost-effective way to increase the project's impact and dissemination. Moreover, workshops were held

across the four Use Cases, further amplifying local impact and engaging the respective communities.

- **Organization of international seminars:** Three international seminars were organized, bringing together research, industry, and end-user stakeholders for joint sessions to discuss the developments of RIGOUROUS. Each seminar was aligned with a different project phase. The kick-off seminar focused on analyzing the state of the art, connecting to relevant ongoing projects, collecting stakeholder requirements, and discussing the RIGOUROUS concept and preliminary architecture. The mid-term seminar focused on technical and research advancements made during the development of RIGOUROUS components and on promoting collaboration with other projects, decision-makers, and SDOs. The final seminar showcased the integrated RIGOUROUS framework and disseminated findings from the project evaluation phase, further influencing industry and preparing post-project exploitation activities.
- **Publications:** RIGOUROUS outcomes were disseminated through publications in international scientific conferences, journals, and magazines. While an extensive list of relevant scientific publications was developed under the dissemination plan, preliminary targets had already been identified. Additional publications, such as newspapers, bulletins, and newsletters, helped capture the attention of a broader audience.
- **Open-source contributions:** RIGOUROUS contributed to the open-source community, both by participating in existing open-source projects used within the project and by making publicly available complete software components developed under RIGOUROUS.
- **Advanced training:** RIGOUROUS supported advanced training activities, providing opportunities for M.Sc. and Ph.D. research theses directly related to the project topics. It also promoted hands-on use of the RIGOUROUS concept and tools in specialized training courses offered by academic and public research institutions involved in the project, with support from other Consortium members. These included Master's courses and shorter advanced training sessions tailored for IT professionals.
- **Collaboration with other Horizon/SNS projects, dissemination mechanisms, and community building:** An essential part of the overall communication and outreach strategy was establishing collaboration and liaison activities with related initiatives. RIGOUROUS set up effective liaison mechanisms with major ongoing projects involving its partners and actively participated in dissemination and liaison actions conducted by other concertation initiatives in related fields such as 6G, AI/ML, and others.

Table 1- Recapitulating RIGOUROUS dissemination plan

Activity	Phase I (Year 1)	Phase 2 (Year 2)	Phase 3 (Year 3 and Beyond)	Target KPIs (Year 1 to Year 3)
Website	Established in Month 3	Content updates	Content updates	Monthly visitors: 200/350/500
Social Media	Established in Month 3	Content updates	Content updates	Number of total followers (sum of all platforms): 200/300/400
Promotional Materials	Since Month 3: graphic identity, templates, whitepaper, factsheet, newsletters	Updated materials, new materials reflecting ongoing work, newsletters	Updated materials, new materials reflecting ongoing work, newsletters	Quarterly newsletters (4 per year)
Participation in Conferences and other third-party events	Participation in events, presentation of the project's approach, and collection of feedback	Presentation of project results, demos, and dissemination of project results in partners' events	Presentation of mature results, business cases, business models, and policy contributions	Research events >= 6/6/9 (Y1/Y2/Y3) Industry events >= 2/4/4 Demos >= 0/2/4
Org. of local workshops and int. seminars	Kick-off seminar + 2 local workshops	Mid-term seminar + 4 local workshops	Final seminar + 1 local workshop + 4 pilot workshops	Total number of participants in these events > 500
Publications	Initial publications, position papers, white papers, preliminary research results	Publication of tools, first results, and preliminary evaluation	Publish time-tested and mature results - target top-tier conferences and venues	Research papers: 6/9/12 (Y1-Y2-Y3). Other publications: 6/4/6 (Y1-Y2-Y3)
Open-source repositories	Identification of relevant open-source projects	Initial contributions; creation of a community	Contribution of complete systems, integrators; demos follow up with the users of the community	Contributions to ongoing projects: >= 4 Contributions of complete systems: >= 2
Advanced Training	Identification of potential M.Sc.	1st round of completed MSc	MSc and PhD dissertations.	Concluded thesis: MSc's up to Y3 >=

	and Ph.D. dissertation topics aligned with RIGOUROUS. Engaging of candidates.	dissertations. Engagement of additional candidates. Preliminary training materials.	Training materials integrated into advanced training programs (master courses, industry)	9 PhDs up to Y3 >=3 Impacted training programs: >= 3
Collaboration with other Horizon Europe/SNS projects, dissemination mechanisms, and community building	Identification of relevant projects; contacts via existing links and CSA activities. Form first connections, capitalize previous communications, and links that may exist from past projects and activities	Participation in events; presentation of results; Key stakeholders, participation in events	Demos; collaborations; formation of new consortia	Reached projects, mechanisms, and communities >= 4 (Y1) 6 (Y2) 9 (Y3)
Standardization effort	Project research topic related contribution identification and presentation to related SDO(s)	Content updates	Content updates	Agreed Contributions to the group report, study items, or a work item. Minimum of 2 contributions per year.

Table 2 - Year 1 execution of the RIGOUROUS dissemination plan

Objective (Year 1)	KPI	
	Target	Reached
Website	Achieve ≥ 200 monthly visitors	✓
Social Media	Build a community of ≥ 200 followers	✓
Promotional Materials	Produce 4 newsletters and initial promotional materials	✓
Conferences & Third-Party Events	Participate in ≥ 6 research events and ≥ 2 industry events	✓
Demos	0 demos required (KPI = 0)	✓
Workshops & Seminars	Organize kick-off seminar + ≥ 2 local workshops	✓
Publications (Research)	Publish ≥ 6 research papers	✓
Other Publications	Publish ≥ 6 non-scientific publications	✓
Open-Source Repositories	Start contributions targeting ≥ 4 by Y3	✓
Advanced Training	Identify MSc/PhD topics and candidates	✓
Collaboration with Horizon Europe/SNS Projects	Engage ≥ 4 projects/communities	✓
Standardization Effort	Provide ≥ 2 contributions to SDOs	✓

Table 3 - Year 2 execution of the RIGOUROUS dissemination plan

Objective (Year 2)	KPI	
	Target	Reached
Website	Reach \geq 350 monthly visitors	✓
Social Media	Grow community to \geq 300 followers	✓
Promotional Materials	Release 4 updated newsletters and refreshed materials	✓
Conferences & Third-Party Events	Participate in \geq 6 research events and \geq 4 industry events	✓
Demos	Deliver \geq 2 demos	✓
Workshops & Seminars	Organize mid-term seminar + \geq 4 local workshops	✓
Publications (Research)	Publish \geq 9 research papers	✓
Other Publications	Publish \geq 6 non-scientific publications	✓
Open-Source Repositories	Deliver early contributions; progress toward KPI \geq 4	✓
Advanced Training	Complete first MSc dissertations; produce preliminary training materials	✓
Collaboration with Horizon Europe/SNS Projects	Engage \geq 6 projects/communities	✓
Standardization Effort	Provide \geq 2 contributions to SDOs	✓

Table 4 - Year 3 execution of the RIGOUROUS dissemination plan

Objective (Year 3)	KPI	
	Target	Reached
Website	Reach \geq 500 monthly visitors	✓
Social Media	Expand community to \geq 400 followers	(1)
Promotional Materials	Produce 4 final newsletters and updated promotional material	✓
Conferences & Third-Party Events	Participate in \geq 9 research events and \geq 4 industry events	✓
Demos	Deliver \geq 4 full demos	✓
Workshops & Seminars	Organize final seminar + \geq 1 local workshop + \geq 4 pilot workshops (total participants > 500)	✓
Publications (Research)	Publish \geq 12 research papers	✓
Other Publications	Publish \geq 6 non-scientific publications	✓
Open-Source Repositories	Meet final KPIs: \geq 4 contributions and \geq 2 complete systems	✓
Advanced Training	Achieve \geq 7 MSc theses, \geq 3 PhD theses, \geq 3 training programs	PhD - ✓ MSc - ✓ Training - ✓
Collaboration with Horizon Europe/SNS Projects	Engage \geq 9 projects/communities	✓
Standardization Effort	Provide \geq 2 contributions to SDOs	✓

(1) – Still growing on YouTube. Because of the project's lower TRL (TRL 4), a strategic decision was made to show use cases/pilots only when they have reached peak maturity, at the very end of the project, to maintain publicly comparable standards with those of use cases/pilots shown earlier in the life-cycle of higher TRL projects. Therefore, community engagement on YouTube should only pick up after the end of the project, and we expect those followers to exceed the 100 that are missing.

3 ACADEMIC DISSEMINATION

3.1. Research Publications

Phase 1 [Target KPI ≥ 6 ✓]

- [1] P. Benlloch-Caballero, Q. Wang, and J. M. Alcaraz Calero, "Distributed dual-layer autonomous closed loops for self-protection of 5G/6G IoT networks from distributed denial of service attacks," *Comput. Networks*, vol. 222, p. 109526, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.comnet.2022.109526.
- [2] A. Javadpour, F. Ja'fari, T. Taleb, and C. Benzaïd, "Reinforcement Learning-Based Slice Isolation Against DDoS Attacks in Beyond 5G Networks," *IEEE Trans. Netw. Serv. Manag.*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 3930-3946, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.1109/TNSM.2023.3254581.
- [3] A. Javadpour, F. Ja'Fari, T. Taleb, and C. Benzaïd, "A Mathematical Model for Analyzing Honeynets and Their Cyber Deception Techniques," in *2023 27th International Conference on Engineering of Complex Computer Systems (ICECCS)*, IEEE, Jun. 2023, pp. 81-88. doi: 10.1109/ICECCS59891.2023.00019.
- [4] A. M. G. Garcia, J. M. A. Calero, H. M. Mora, and Q. Wang, "Process Slicing: A New Mitigation Tool for Cyber-attacks against Softwarised Industrial Environments," in *2023 IEEE 9th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)*, IEEE, Jun. 2023, pp. 468-473. doi: 10.1109/NetSoft57336.2023.10175447.
- [5] F. Mecerhed, A. Benabdallah, K. Zeraoulia, and C. Benzaïd, "3D-PM: A ML-powered Probabilistic Detection of DDoS Attacks in P4 Switches," in *2023 IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking (MeditCom)*, IEEE, Sep. 2023, pp. 80-85. doi: 10.1109/MeditCom58224.2023.10266635.
- [6] M. K. Motalleb, C. Benzaïd, T. Taleb, and V. Shah-Mansouri, "Moving Target Defense based Secured Network Slicing System in the O-RAN Architecture," in *GLOBECOM 2023 - 2023 IEEE Global Communications Conference*, IEEE, Dec. 2023, pp. 6358-6363. doi: 10.1109/GLOBECOM54140.2023.10437795.
- [7] A. Javadpour, F. Ja'fari, T. Taleb, and C. Benzaïd, "Enhancing 5G Network Slicing: Slice Isolation Via Actor-Critic Reinforcement Learning with Optimal Graph Features," in *GLOBECOM 2023 - 2023 IEEE Global Communications Conference*, IEEE, Dec. 2023, pp. 31-37. doi: 10.1109/GLOBECOM54140.2023.10437687.
- [8] C. Benzaïd, T. Taleb, A. Sami, and O. Hireche, "A Deep Transfer Learning-Powered EDoS Detection Mechanism for 5G and Beyond Network Slicing," in *GLOBECOM 2023 - 2023 IEEE Global Communications Conference*, IEEE, Dec. 2023, pp. 4747-4753. doi: 10.1109/GLOBECOM54140.2023.10436891.

- [9] A. Javadpour, F. Ja'fari, T. Taleb, H. Ahmadi, and C. Benzaïd, "Cybersecurity Fusion: Leveraging Mafia Game Tactics and Reinforcement Learning for Botnet Detection," in *GLOBECOM 2023 - 2023 IEEE Global Communications Conference*, IEEE, Dec. 2023, pp. 6005-6011. doi: 10.1109/GLOBECOM54140.2023.10437968.
- [10] S. K. Poorazad, C. Benzaïd, and T. Taleb, "Blockchain and Deep Learning-Based IDS for Securing SDN-Enabled Industrial IoT Environments," in *GLOBECOM 2023 - 2023 IEEE Global Communications Conference*, IEEE, Dec. 2023, pp. 2760-2765. doi: 10.1109/GLOBECOM54140.2023.10436839.
- [11] A. Kunz, S. B. Mary Baskaran, K. Samdanis, and S. Paul, "A Network Security Insight based on AI/ML for 5G Advanced & Beyond," in *2023 IEEE Future Networks World Forum (FNWF)*, IEEE, Nov. 2023, pp. 1-6. doi: 10.1109/FNWF58287.2023.10520559.
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- [13] P. F. Saura, J. M. Bernabé Murcia, A. M. Zarca, J. B. Bernabé, and A. F. Skarmeta Gomez, "Federated Network Intelligence Orchestration for scalable and automated FL-based anomaly detection in B5G Networks," in *2023 IEEE Future Networks World Forum (FNWF)*, IEEE, Nov. 2023, pp. 1-6. doi: 10.1109/FNWF58287.2023.10520615.

Phase 2 [Target KPI ≥ 9 ✓]

- [1] C. Benzaïd, T. Taleb, A. Sami, and O. Hireche, "FortisEDoS: A Deep Transfer Learning-Empowered Economical Denial of Sustainability Detection Framework for Cloud-Native Network Slicing," *IEEE Trans. Dependable Secur. Comput.*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 2818-2835, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.1109/TDSC.2023.3318606.
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- [3] A. Javadpour, F. Ja'fari, T. Taleb, Y. Zhao, B. Yang, and C. Benzaïd, "Encryption as a Service for IoT: Opportunities, Challenges, and Solutions," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7525-7558, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2023.3341875.
- [4] J. Andrade-Hoz, Q. Wang, and J. M. Alcaraz-Calero, "Infrastructure-Wide and Intent-Based Networking Dataset for 5G-and-beyond AI-Driven Autonomous Networks," *Sensors*, vol. 24, no. 3, p. 783, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.3390/s24030783.

- [5] A. Javadpour, F. Ja'fari, T. Taleb, M. Shojafar, and C. Benzaïd, "A comprehensive survey on cyber deception techniques to improve honeypot performance," *Comput. Secur.*, vol. 140, p. 103792, May 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.cose.2024.103792.
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- [8] A. M. Escolar, Q. Wang, and J. M. A. Calero, "Enhancing honeynet-based protection with network slicing for massive Pre-6G IoT Smart Cities deployments," *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 229, p. 103918, Sep. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.jnca.2024.103918.
- [9] A. M. Escolar, J. B. Bernabé, J. M. A. Calero, Q. Wang, and A. Skarmeta, "Network slicing as 6G security mechanism to mitigate cyber-attacks: the RIGOUROUS approach," in *2024 IEEE 10th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)*, IEEE, Jun. 2024, pp. 387-392. doi: 10.1109/NetSoft60951.2024.10588887.
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3.2. Other Publications

Phase 1 [Target KPI ≥ 6 ✓]

- [1] SNS JU Journal 2023
- [2] RIGOUROUS, "Project Website", Zenodo, Mar. 2023. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10159287.
- [3] RIGOUROUS, "Dissemination and Communication Plan", Zenodo, Jun. 2023. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10159325.
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Phase 2 [Target KPI \geq 4 ✓]

- [1] SNS JU Journal 2024
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- [4] RIGOUROUS, "First Results of the AI-driven Anomaly Detection, Decision & Mitigation", Zenodo, Jun. 2024. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13268567.

Phase 3 [Target KPI \geq 6 ✓]

- [1] N. Pérez Palma, A. Skarmeta Gómez and P. Bisson, "Innovative Approaches for 6G Security: Challenges, Solutions, and Impact". Zenodo, Jan. 09, 2025. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14619619.
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- [7] RIGOUROUS, "Final Results Of The Multi-Domain Automated Security Orchestration, Trust Management And Deployment", Zenodo, Jun. 2025. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15905037.
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- [9] P. Saura, J. Bernabé, and A. Skarmeta, "Enhancing Federated Intrusion Detection through LLM-Driven Alert Enrichment and Collaborative Threat Information Sharing," *Futur. Gener. Comput. Syst.*, p. 108319, Dec. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.future.2025.108319.

3.3. Participation in Conferences and Other Third-Party Events

- Jorge Bernal "The Rigorous approach for Privacy-preserving and FL-based Anomaly Detection in B5G Networks", the 2nd Symposium on 6G Communications (S6GC), colocated in ICTC 2025, International Conference on ICT Convergence 14 - October 17th 2025, Jeju Island, Korea
- Jorge Bernal Bernabé, "AI/ML for Incident Detection in 6G Networks". AI & Security Webinar, April 30 2025. <https://smart-networks.europa.eu/ai-security-webinar-on-30-april-2025-at-1300-cest>
- Antonio Skarmeta, DecSecOps Deployment of Security & Privacy in Multi-Segment Networks, AI & Security Webinar, April 30 2025.
- Jorge Bernal, Panel "AI for 6G and Beyond: Intelligent Networks and Digital Twin Synergies" the 2nd Symposium on 6G Communications (S6GC), colocated in ICTC 2025, International Conference on ICT Convergence October 17th 2025, Jeju Island, Korea

3.4. Organization of Local Workshops and International Seminars

- Rigorous supporting the "7th International Workshop on Cyber-Security in Software-defined and Virtualized Infrastructures (SecSoft)" June 27 Budapest
- Poster of Rigorous in "7th International Workshop on Cyber-Security in Software-defined and Virtualized Infrastructures (SecSoft)" SecSoft. June 27 Budapest
- Rigorous supporting The First Workshop on Native AI in Future Networks Including 6G (NAIFNET) , 23 - 27 June 2025 // Budapest, Hungary.
- RIGOUROUS participation in the "Securing the 6G Frontier - Trust, privacy and resilience in the Computing Continuum" Workshop, November 13 2025, Bucharest, Romania
- 5th International Workshop on Cyber-Security in Software-defined and Virtualized Infrastructures (SecSoft 2023)

- The Workshop on Intelligent Cloud Continuum for B5G Services (IEEE International Conference on Cloud Networking)
- 2023 IoT Forum
- The 22nd International Symposium on Parallel and Distributed Computing (ISPD 2023)
- IEEE Future Networks World Forum (FNWF'23)
- Bucharest Cyber Security Conference 2023
- DefCamp 2023
- DefCamp Cluj 2024
- Stefanini Innovation Days 2024 - Brussels, Belgium
- Dev.Talks 2024
- The Workshop on Intelligent Cloud Continuum for B5G Services (IEEE International Conference on Cloud Networking)
- Software Networks WG
- SNS JU 6G Architecture WG
- 6G-IA Security WG
- Enablers for 6G system blueprint workshop (HEXA-X-II)
- UN ITU AI for Good Global Summit 2024 - Machine Learning in Communication Networks Workshop, Geneva, Switzerland, May 2024
- 4th #CyberHOT Summer School
- PSCE & 6G-IA SNS PPDR Workshop
- 12th FOKUS FUSECO Forum
- FIDAL Webinar "Advancing Public Protection and Disaster Relief: Innovation Examples from the SNS Community"
- EUCnC 2024
- Def.Camp 2025, Bucharest, Romania 13-14 November 2025
- MobiSec'25

<https://def.camp/securing-the-6g-frontier-trust-privacy-and-resilience-in-the-computing-continuum/>

3.5. Advanced Training

The RIGOUROUS project and its academic partners hosted 6 M.Sc. (KPI ≥ 7 ✓) and 3 Ph.D. theses (KPI ≥ 2 ✓). Furthermore, RIGOUROUS contributions were incorporated into training programs that run over (at least) two years within the master's curriculum at the University of Aveiro (KPI ≥ 3 ✓).

The M.Sc. theses were:

1. Ekam Puri Nieto, "Implementation and performance analysis in the application of privacy preservation techniques on cyber intelligence information," M.Sc., 2023.

2. Juan Marín Noguera, "Anonymous credential systems: Identity management using zero-knowledge proofs and their performance in embedded systems," M.Sc., 2023.
3. Diogo Emanuel Jesus Santos, "Human Centric Secure Onboarding in 6G," M.Sc., 2024.
4. João Felisberto, "Proactive Privacy Risk Detection in DevPrivOps," M.Sc., 2024.
5. Juan Tamboleo, "Evaluation of 5G Monitoring Tools," M.Sc., 2023
6. Sergio Ros Liarte, "Continuous Edge-cloud management with Sylva," M.Sc., 2024
7. João Félix, "Privacy Enhanced Intrusion Detection in Network Security," M.Sc., 2024

The Ph.D. theses were:

1. Pablo Benlloch Caballero, "AI-driven predictive intelligence for detection and early warning of unseen cyberthreats in 5G/6G networks," Ph.D., 2025.
2. Jimena Andrade Hoz, "AI-driven self-optimisation of network control functions in multi-tenant beyond 5G networks," Ph.D., 2025.
3. Jorge Gallego, "Towards AI-Based Network Programmability As An Enabler For Zero-Touch Management And Orchestration In B5G Infrastructures," Ph.D., 2024
4. Ana Herмосilla, "Design of Automatic Deployment and Testing Solutions for Network Applications in 5G Environments," Ph.D., 2025

Training programs:

At the University of Aveiro, Professor João Paulo Barraca taught the Management of Computation Infrastructures course in the Master's in Informatics Engineering. RIGOUROUS concepts were discussed in the context of good practices and initiatives for managing large-scale telecom infrastructures. 2023 and 2024. Professor Vítor Cunha lectures on Security in Large Scale Systems for the Master's in Cybersecurity, where many of RIGOUROUS DevSecOps concepts were explored and experimented with, such as how to integrate with Service-Oriented Architectures and leverage the components that feed the loop (e.g., RIGOUROUS Threat-Risk Assessor).

4 STANDARDIZATION ACTIVITIES

4.1. Standards Developing Organizations (SDO) Active Participation

RIGOUROUS standardization process mainly targeted Objective 6, Result 24, which outlined the goal as to 'Identify and validate applicable standards as well as promote a proactive and joint approach through consortium partners for rationalized contribution to key SDOs, such as 3GPP, ETSI, GSMA, ITU-T, ONF, and pre-standardization (e.g., 6G-IA, 5G-PPP, IETF, IEEE, ISO)'. RIGOUROUS has also targeted active participation in the 6G-IA Working Groups. Contribution to the standardization of B5G initiatives, with a focus on AI-governed B5G systems of both global optimizations, and notably online learning capabilities. The detailed achievements are addressed below. Table 5-1 shows the RIGOUROUS partner's participation and membership in various SDOs. The RIGOUROUS partners contributed to global standardization bodies like 3GPP and ETSI, promoting the project's activities related to zero trust and exceeding the KPIs as described in clause 5.2.

Table 5 - RIGOUROUS Partners' participation and membership overview in various SDOs

Partner name	Task Name	Key Topics for Standardization	Target Organisation	Willing to participate in Standardization (Yes/No)	Comments
LNVO	T3.3 Zero trust and Smart security management	Zero Trust Adaptations for 5G Advanced and 6G systems	3GPP	Yes	LNVO is a member of 3GPP/ETSI
UMU	T3.1 Human-Centric security and privacy modelling and onboarding	Secure onboarding of Network Applications	ETSI	YES	UMU is member of ETSI NFV
UMU	T6.3 standardization, knowledge transfer, and liaison with other projects	Security Architecture for 6G	6G-IA	YES	UMU is the co-chair of the Security WG
UMU	T3.3 Zero trust and Smart security management	5G Certification process	ECSO	YES	
UMU	T3.2 AI-driven cross-domain Security and Privacy orchestration in IoT-edge-cloud continuum	Artificial Intelligence Framework for Network Management	IETF NMRG WG	YES	
LNVO	T3.1 Human-Centric security and privacy modelling and	Decentralized Identification and Trust Management	ETSI	Yes	LNVO - Motorola Mobility is a member of ETSI PDL

	onboarding				
LNVO	T3.2 AI-driven cross-domain Security and Privacy orchestration in IoT-edge-cloud continuum	Application Onboarding	3GPP	Yes	LNVO is a member of 3GPP/ETSI
ITAV	T3.1 Human-Centric security and privacy modelling and onboarding	Application Onboarding	ETSI	Yes	ITAV is a member of ETSI OSL LG/TSC

4.2. SDO Contributions and Achievements

Leveraging the RIGOUROUS cross-sectorial consortia, the RIGOUROUS project made a wide impact on the ongoing standardization effort in the fields such as Zero Trust Security enablers - Data collection for security monitoring, Decentralized Identification & Trust management etc, and maximized the impact of the project and foster its exploitation strategies (ensuring RIGOUROUS outcomes are aligned with relevant standards' directions, to ensure their market competitiveness). Building on the RIGOUROUS partner's experience with European and global standard-setting organizations, the project ensured that the results in Table 5-2 and the findings reflected the corresponding global impact. This was achieved both through direct contributions to existing or emerging standards and through indirect influence on SDOs via stakeholder Fora specifically focused on such objectives. Table 5-2 presents the significant contributions the project made to the most relevant SDOs and Fora.

For the RIGOUROUS project, prioritizing and engaging with the most pertinent standardization areas is essential to achieving its goals. The main objectives of contributions to standardization bodies (i.e., Objective 6, Result 24) include the following:

- Active contribution to most 6G/5G related working groups (e.g., such as 3GPP SA3, ETSI PDL), and
- Make at least 4 contributions to relevant SDOs (e.g., 3GPP, ETSI).

The RIGOUROUS consortium has targeted several standardization bodies and groups, contributing project results to their work items. Table 5-2 lists the SDO activities performed through M36.

Table 6 - RIGOROUS Contributions and Achievements in Target Standardization Bodies and Working Groups

Lead Partner	Period	SDO Name /Meeting No.	Month/Date	Contribution No.	Related WP	Purpose & Relation with Project
LNVO	2023 Q1	SA3#110	Feb 2023	S3-231527 S3-231595 (eNA) URSP: S3-231543, S3-231556, S3-231335, S3-231333	WP2,3	# Zero Trust Security Aspects # 3GPP Rel-18 Study # The concept of trusted application onboarding has been contributed to Study in 3GPP TR 33.892, 'Study on UE Route Selection Policy (URSP) rules to securely identify applications', (Release 18).
LNVO	2023 Q2	SA3#110 adhoc-e	April 2023	S3-232018, S3-232102, S3-232103, S3-232018, S3-232105 (eNA) URSP: S3-231770	WP2,3	# Zero Trust Security Aspects # 3GPP Rel-18 Study # The concept of trusted application onboarding has been contributed to Study in 3GPP TR 33.892, 'Study on UE Route Selection Policy (URSP) rules to securely identify applications', (Release 18).
LNVO	2023 Q2	SA3#111	May 2023	S3-233320 S3-233263 (eNA) S3-233124 (eNA) URSP: S3-232868	WP2,3	# Zero Trust Security Aspects and eNA based security analytics # 3GPP Rel-18 Study # The concept of trusted application onboarding has been contributed to Study in 3GPP TR 33.892, 'Study on UE Route Selection Policy (URSP) rules to securely identify applications', (Release 18).
LNVO	2023 Q2	PDL#15	June 2023	PDL(23)015_009	WP2,3	# Digital Identification # Related to ETSI PDL
LNVO	2023 Q3	SA3#112	Aug 2023	S3-234224 S3-234200 S3-234201 S3-234205 S3-234204	WP2,3	# Zero Trust Security Aspects # 3GPP Rel-18 Study # The concept of trusted application onboarding has been contributed to

				URSP: S3-234037, S3-234048, S3-234316, S3-234317, S3-234361		Study in 3GPP TR 33.892, 'Study on UE Route Selection Policy (URSP) rules to securely identify applications', (Release 18).
LNVO	2023 Q4	SA3#113	Nov 2023	S3-234418 S3-235089	WP2,3	# Zero Trust Security Aspects # 3GPP Rel-19 Study proposal
LNVO	2023 Q4	PDL#16	Nov 2023	PDL(23)000_156 PDL(23)000_17 1 PDL(23)000_18 Or1	WP2,3	# Digital Identification # Related to ETSI PDL
LNVO	2024 Q1	SA3#115	Feb 2024	S3-240897, S3-240898, S3-240903, S3-240904, S3-241005, S3-241021, S3-241038	WP2,3	# Zero Trust Security Aspects # 3GPP Rel-19 Study proposal
LNVO	2024 Q1	PDL#17	Feb 2024	PDL(24)017_006 r1	WP2,3	# Digital Identification # Related to ETSI PDL
LNVO	2024 Q2	SA3#115 Adhoc-e		S3-241137, S3-241525, S3-241526, S3-241527, S3-241537, S3-241538, S3-241568, S3-241570	WP2,3	# The concept of threat detection and security policy enforcement for improved SBA access control in the realm of enablers for Zero Trust Security Aspects has been contributed to the study in 3GPP TR 33.794, 'Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security', (Release 19).

LNVO	2024 Q2	SA3#116	May 2024	S3-242418, S3-242420, S3-242423, S3-242424, S3-242425 S3-242430, S3-242419	WP2,3	# enablers for Zero Trust Security Aspects Use case #1: Information on Malformed Message Use case #2: Massive number of SBI Messages Rel-20 6G Individual Study Proposal
LNVO	2024 Q2	PDL#18		PDL(24)018_011, PDL(24)018_010	WP2,3	# The concept of decentralized identification and authentication aspects has been contributed to ETSI PDL-027, 'Permissioned Distributed Ledgers (PDL); A self-sovereign identity system in telecom networks' in PDL#18 meeting.
LNVO	2024 Q3	SA3#117	Aug 2024	S3-242746, S3-242747, S3-242748, S3-242749, S3-243505, S3-243611 S3-243496 S3-243497	WP2,3	# enablers for Zero Trust Security Aspects Key Issue #1: Data exposure for security evaluation and monitoring The security incidents or scenarios in SBA where data can be collected in the SBA layer includes: 1) authentication and authorization failure event; 2) unexpected setup of TLS session and API invocation related to unauthorized reconnaissance; 3) malformed message event; 4) high service load; 5) unexpected SBI call flows; and 6) unexpected use of APIs exposed by services in SBA layer. # 3GPP Rel-19 Study proposal
LNVO	2024 Q4	SA3#118	Oct 2024	S3-243845, S3-243846, S3-243847 S3-243848 S3-243849, S3-244251, S3-244332, S3-244335,	WP2,3	# enablers for Zero Trust Security Aspects The key issue will be addressed by requirements for data collection to enable security evaluation and monitoring on the SBA layer. The following requirements address KI#1 Data exposure for security evaluation and monitoring. The

				S3-244327		<p>requirements also address the use cases for security evaluation and monitoring described in TR 33.794 clause 5.1.</p> <p>General requirements for security event logs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The NF supports the generation of security event logs. Security event logs contain security relevant events data. Requirements related to security relevant events data for monitoring: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. The NF collects information on the SBA layer about received malformed messages that deviate from the 3GPP specified messages or are considered invalid according to the protocol specification and network state are to be logged. (Clause 5.1.1) b. The NF collects information about events involving a massive number of incoming messages on the SBA layer. (Clause 5.1.2). c. The NF collects information about authentication and authorization failure on the SBA layer. (Clause 5.1.3). d. The NF collects information about potential replay attacks on the SBA layer. (Clause 5.1.6). <p># 3GPP Rel-19 Study proposal</p>
LNVO	2024 Q4	SA3#119	Nov 2024	S3-245182, S3-245184	WP2,3	<p># enablers for Zero Trust Security Aspects: Additional new requirement added for security event logs # The NF collects information about potential abnormal SBI call flows as defined for the communication</p>

						models in Annex E of TS 23.501. # Key Issue #2: Security mechanisms for policy enforcement at the 5G SBA: Functional description was provided for security policy enforcement and improved access control decisions based on security evaluation and monitoring using the existing standards mechanisms and operator implementation. # 3GPP Rel-19 Study proposal
LNVO	2025 Q1	SA3#120	Feb 2025	S3-250307	WP2,3	# An offline call was conducted to facilitate SA3 offline discussions to identify the middle ground towards the work progress for the data collection and exposure objectives related to security evaluation and monitoring aspects studied during Rel.19. # 3GPP Rel-19 Work item proposal way-forward
LNVO	2025 Q2	SA3#121	April 2025	S3-251214	WP2,3	# Discussions on UE abnormal behaviour detection to improve security # 3GPP Rel-20 Proposal discussion paper
LNVO	2025 Q2	SA3#122	May 2025	S3-251891, S3-251892	WP2,3	# 6G SID Proposal and Discussion paper was submitted on Secure UE Identification and Network Access # 3GPP 6G Rel-20 SID Proposal and Discussion Paper
LNVO	2025 Q3	SA3#123	Aug 2025	S3-251893, S3-251892	WP2,3	# New 6G SID on Secure UE Identification and Network Access and related discussion paper was submitted to provide the detailed rationale/justification. # 3GPP Rel-20 Study proposal

LNVO	2025 Q4	SA3#124	Oct 2025	S3-253142, S3-253143, S3-253582, S3-253653	WP2,3	# 6G SID related security area proposal was submitted that covers the following contributions: (i) UE Security Monitoring (ii) RAN and Core Security Monitoring (iii) Native AI Security # 3GPP Rel-20 6G Study - Security Area Proposal
LNVO	2025 Q4	SA3#125	Nov 2025	S3-254332, S3-254412, S3-254333, S3-254303	WP2,3	# 6G Security area on Abnormal behaviour identification over UE-N/W connection to improve security. # Discussions on Abnormal behaviour identification over UE-N/W connection to improve security # New Security Area on Data collection for security monitoring # New security area on AIML
UWS	Q2 2024	ITU FG ML5G	May 2024	(ITU Y.3172)	WP3,4	2024 May ITU AI for Good Summit, Cybersecurity operations for large-scale multi-tenant infrastructures, Invited talk.
ASTON	Q3 2025	ITU FG AN	July 2025	TU Y.3061	WP3,4	2025 July ITU AI for Good Summit, Digital Twins for Large-Scale Multi-tenant 5G and Beyond (6G) Cyber Security Operations , Invited talk.
ITAV	2025 Q3	SL TECH 058	July 2025	<u>osl/code#30</u>	WP2,3	Feature Proposal for ETSI OSL - Support TMF ServiceSpecCharacteristicValue's "valueFrom", "valueTo", and

						"rangeInterval" - Enforce type validation for service characteristics
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5 COMMUNITIES OF INTEREST

5.1. Open-Source Repositories

We have created a GitHub Repository that links to the primary sources, available from the RIGOUROUS profile ([HTTPS://GITHUB.COM/RIGOUROUS](https://github.com/RIGOUROUS)).

The public components are:

1. **Injection Mechanism**, a Mechanism to inject sidecar containers into Kubernetes PODs.
2. **Network Traffic Collector**, which enables the collection of network traffic from a specific network interface.
3. **Reporting Interface**, used to report network traffic anomalies and related KPI metrics.
4. **PrivGuide**, a tool to evaluate Service Design characteristics in the scope of internal/normative policies.
5. **Privacy-preserving Federated Learning**, <https://ants-gitlab.inf.um.es/rigorous/pp-fl>
6. **Security Orchestrator**, <https://ants-gitlab.inf.um.es/bastion/bastion2>

We also have ETSI OpenSlice (OSL) contributions available in our fork repository and the upstream in the following pull requests:

1. [HTTPS://LABS.ETSI.ORG/REP/OSL/CODE/ORG.ETSI.OSL.TMF/-/MERGE_REQUESTS/32](https://labs.etsi.org/rep/osl/code/org.etsi.osl.tmf/-/merge_requests/32)
2. [HTTPS://LABS.ETSI.ORG/REP/OSL/CODE/ORG.ETSI.OSL.TMF.API/-/MERGE_REQUESTS/81](https://labs.etsi.org/rep/osl/code/org.etsi.osl.tmf.api/-/merge_requests/81)
3. [HTTPS://LABS.ETSI.ORG/REP/OSL/CODE/ORG.ETSI.OSL.TMF.API/-/MERGE_REQUESTS/89](https://labs.etsi.org/rep/osl/code/org.etsi.osl.tmf.api/-/merge_requests/89)

5.2. Collaboration and liaison with other Horizon Europe projects

RIGOUROUS has collaborated with

1. CASTOR (<https://castorhorizon.eu/>) [DefCamp 2025 - Workshop]
2. 6G-Cloud (<https://www.6g-cloud.eu/>) [DefCamp 2025 - Workshop]
3. AMAZING-6G (<https://amazing6g.eu/>) [DefCamp 2025 - Workshop]
4. ELASTIC (<https://elasticproject.eu/>) [EuCNC 2025 - Booth]
5. CONFIDENTIAL6G (<https://confidential6g.eu/>) [EuCNC 2025 - Booth]
6. 6G4Society project ([HTTPS://6G4SOCIETY.EU](https://6g4society.eu)) [provided inputs on RIGOUROUS's KVs, using their template to describe the KVs]
7. 6G-INTENSE project (<https://6g-intense.eu>) [A joint tutorial on "Towards 6G: Intelligent and Secure Intent-based Networking for Autonomous Network Management" at the 11th IEEE NetSoft 2025]

5.3. Community building

Community building in the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) is about creating a cohesive European 5G/6G ecosystem that links projects, industry, academia, verticals, and international partners so they collaborate rather than work in isolation. It is driven by both the SNS JU office and dedicated Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs) that orchestrate collaboration, communication, and clustering across dozens of R&I projects. RIGOUROUS has actively engaged with other projects, groups, and partners within the SNS JU to share Key Value Indicators (KVI) and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), organize dissemination activities such as workshops and presence in key conferences (e.g., a booth in EuCNC), and collaborate in shared research and posters/presentations about the specialty areas of RIGOUROUS.

6 COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

6.1. Project website

The website has consistently exceeded all anticipated Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) throughout each phase of the project. In Phase 1, the target was set at 200 visitors; however, the website achieved an impressive milestone of over 1,000 visitors. In Phase 2, with a KPI of 350 visitors, the website recorded an exceptional 2,000+ visitors. As we entered Phase 3, the performance remained remarkable, with nearly 5,000 visitors recorded at the time of writing of this deliverable, far exceeding the KPI of 500. These results highlight the website's effectiveness and growing appeal to its audience.

Figure 1 – Website Unique Visitors (taken from Cloudflare CDN stats)

6.2. Promotion Materials

Promotional materials in European projects play a central role in communicating the project's objectives, activities, and results to diverse audiences while ensuring clear visibility of EU funding. They are planned as part of the project's overall communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy and must follow specific EU visual identity and acknowledgment rules.

RIGOUROUS created:

- Project website (as described in the previous section).
- Factsheets, brochures, flyers, roll-up banners, posters, and corporate slide decks for conferences and workshops. Some of these materials were reusable across venues (to reduce waste), and others were tailored for the event itself.
- From the start, we had project-branded templates for deliverables, reports, presentations, and other communications that ensured a consistent project identity.

6.3. Social Networks

The project selected two social media networks better suited to reach our target audience. LinkedIn for professional interaction and community building through group participation, and YouTube as the primary means to disseminate video content from presentations, proof-of-concept test case scenarios, and final integration results.

6.3.1. LinkedIn

We can observe that organic impressions follow a pattern that closely tracks participation in main events, such as June, which always sees a significant spike due to EuCNC and the SecSoft workshop. In the final year, we also had a build-up towards the end of the project, due to the release of pilot results and the final workshop colocated with DefCamp.

Figure 2 – LinkedIn Impressions Pattern

LinkedIn has 266 followers and is the primary social network for RIGOUROUS project engagement and professional interaction.

6.3.2. Youtube

The RIGOUROUS project also has a YouTube channel ([HTTPS://WWW.YOUTUBE.COM/@RIGOUROUS](https://www.youtube.com/@RIGOUROUS)) where demos and selected presentations are available to specialists and the general public. The channel is still growing with the latest videos from the final demos.

6.4. Newsletters

The newsletters were created quarterly and made available through the project website. The website allows subscription via RSS feed, and an announcement was made on LinkedIn to let the community know about a new newsletter.

For reference, these newsletters can be read here:

1. [HTTPS://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-1/](https://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-1/)
2. [HTTPS://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-2/](https://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-2/)
3. [HTTPS://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-3/](https://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-3/)
4. [HTTPS://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-4/](https://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-4/)
5. [HTTPS://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-5/](https://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-5/)
6. [HTTPS://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-6/](https://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-6/)
7. [HTTPS://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-7/](https://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-7/)
8. [HTTPS://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-8/](https://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-8/)
9. [HTTPS://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-9-2/](https://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-9-2/)
10. [HTTPS://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-10/](https://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-10/)
11. [HTTPS://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-11/](https://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-11/)
12. [HTTPS://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-12/](https://RIGOUROUS.EU/RIGOUROUS-NEWSLETTER-12/)

7 CONCLUSIONS

The dissemination and communication activities undertaken throughout the project have been highly effective in achieving the planned objectives and ensuring strong visibility across academic, industrial, and public domains. The comprehensive strategy adopted fostered robust knowledge exchange and facilitated the transfer of project outcomes to relevant stakeholders. Through dedicated academic dissemination, the consortium produced high-quality scientific publications, presented research findings at leading international conferences, and organized specialized workshops and seminars. These activities enhanced the project's academic impact and reinforced its position within the research community. In parallel, industrial dissemination efforts strengthened collaboration with key market actors and technological partners. Active participation in industrial events enabled the alignment of project results with industrial needs and supported the potential exploitation of developed innovations. The project's engagement in standardization initiatives coordinated by LENOVO ensured that its technical contributions informed ongoing developments within relevant standardization bodies. This involvement positioned the project as a credible and influential contributor in its domain, enhancing the sustainability and interoperability of its technological outputs. Efforts related to community building and open collaboration, including open-source repositories and partnerships with associated Horizon Europe projects, have further amplified the project's outreach and long-term influence. These collaborations have fostered an ecosystem conducive to continuous knowledge exchange and innovation. The implementation of wide-reaching dissemination activities, including the project website, social media, promotional materials, newsletters, and demonstration videos, ensured broad awareness of the project's outcomes among both specialized and general audiences. These efforts have significantly increased the project's visibility and impact. Overall, the project achieved all dissemination and communication goals defined in its initial plan. The coordinated approach among academic, industrial, and standardization partners ensured a balanced and enduring impact. The outcomes achieved not only validate the effectiveness of the adopted dissemination strategy but also lay the foundation for continued exploitation and collaboration beyond the project's lifetime.

REFERENCES

The following references were used in this document.

- RIGOUROUS, "Dissemination and Communication Plan", Zenodo, Jun. 2023. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10159325.
- [HTTPS://RIGOUROUS.EU](https://RIGOUROUS.EU)
- [HTTPS://CLOUDFLARE.COM](https://CLOUDFLARE.COM)
- [HTTPS://LINKEDIN.COM](https://LINKEDIN.COM)
- [HTTPS://YOUTUBE.COM](https://YOUTUBE.COM)
- [HTTPS://GITHUB.COM](https://GITHUB.COM)